
Efficient Transformers for Financial Data

Prateek Rajput¹ Vladimir Chernyy¹
Nikita Gulkhov¹

Abstract

Many predictive tasks require long term time series modeling which can efficiently capture long range dependencies in the data. Transformers have achieved state of the art results for most standard sequential modeling tasks and the bottleneck for time complexity in the attention matrix of transformers has been tried to be resolved from quadratic to linear complexity by informer and transformer approaches. Since the application of these approaches to financial transactions data is under explored, in this paper we attempt to do so with regards to efficient implementation and high accuracy of prediction.

Github repo:

<https://github.com/Nik212/efficient-transformers-4seqdata>

1. Introduction

Tracking and prediction of transactions data is a complex time series problem attempting to capture dynamics and multiple patterns of spatial and temporal dependencies. It may hold with long term dependencies and thus previous works like (Wen et al., 2017) are rendered limited in their usage since if the dependency ranges from over (48 in this case) some limit in this case the error matrices go into unacceptable ranges.

The self-attention mechanism in Transformers can reduce the maximum length of network signals traveling paths to the minimum possible i.e. $O(1)$ which makes it superior and even SOTA for many long sequence time series forecasting (LSFT) problems.

Such approaches in regards to LSFT data has been tried before with NLP applications and have achieved great results but our experiments with financial data is more intriguing in a sense because there are no semantics in numerical data itself and so the temporal chances in a continuous set of points captured during modeling of such data gives a better representation of architecture performance.

The goal of the following report is to review existing models of efficient transformers. In particular, We discuss theoretical complexities and conduct our own experiments to compare memory usage and inference time some of these models. We use the dataset of high frequency cryptocurrency prices with the task of predicting the next timestamp price. The discussion of the dataset will be in the next sections. Notice that We DO NOT focus on the predictions quality and our main goal is to analyze the memory footprint and inference time. For these tasks, the predictions quality does not matter.

2. Literature Review

In the past 20 years time series forecasting solutions have undergone a progression from basic models like ARIMA (Ariyo et al., 2014) and GBRT (Friedman, 2001) to neural network architectures like RNNs (Lai et al., 2018) and Temporal CNNs (Liu et al., 2021a) but recently transformers have been the most successful and have shown SOTA performance in many sequential data tasks, especially many standard NLP tasks for example machine translation, speech recognition, text generation etc thus transformer approach in general seems to be a very promising one with tasks of sequential modeling.

The unique ability of transformers can be jolted down to its self-attention mechanism which allows it to be capable of extracting linked information in long sequences better than any other approach but the limit to this approach lies in the computational complexity and storage needs to find the attention matrix which grows quadratic to the sequence length and thus acts as the bottleneck for many tasks, especially those which do not have a clear semantic representation and thus cannot use huge pretrained models to create meaningful embeddings (sparse approaches of estimating attention matrix fail in this case). Recently some solutions have come up that pose a potential solution to this problem and this paper is an attempt to test these approaches and create a comparative study.

2.1. Informer and Performer

Our main focus is to test these two approaches on financial data. Informer (Zhou et al., 2021) methodology tries to approach the problem by attempting to fit an arbitrary length of sequence in memory, it has three main points of discussion:

- ProbSparse self-attention mechanism which is a substitute of traditional attention and has both the time complexity and memory usage for dependency alignment of the order of $\mathcal{O}(n \log n)$
- Self-attention distilling to create preferences in stack-

ing layers in order to accumulate long input sequences

- Generative style decoder avoiding cumulative error on inference

The performer approach (Choromanski et al., 2020) on the other hand proposes a new fast attention via positive orthogonal random features (FAVOR+) mechanism which approximates softmax and gaussian kernels while providing theoretical guarantee of being unbiased in estimating attention matrix while at the same time ensuring uniform convergence and low variance of the approximated matrix. For the scope of this study we show just the performance of informer as a PoC for our proposal.

2.2. LogTrans and Pyraformer

Some other approaches to solve the memory and complexity bottleneck which can be tested are:

LogTrans (Li et al., 2019) approach proposes a convolutional self-attention to produce queries and keys in self-attention layers while reducing storage complexity. Pyraformer (Liu et al., 2021b), which proposes a pyramidal attention module (PAM) that uses internal tree structures to summarize features at different scales. The temporal dependencies at different ranges are captured by intra-scale connections using scaled features.

2.3. Embeddings

Positional information like holidays and events can be important in time series so creating learnable timestamps is an important aspect to achieve good performance, the self-attention layers in transformer by itself cannot preserve this positional information and so we will create embeddings for data points to capture this information. Moreover numeric data is unlike NLP data which has different contextual semantic representation and so we believe that trying to test performance on our numeric dataset will be more of a *real* test for transformers to show ability for prediction of sequential data. Although approaches for creating Positional, Token, Fixed, Temporal, TimeFeature and Data can be used to embed the data we have used just the TimeFeature embedding in our experiments.

2.4. Theoretical complexity

Originally, the transformer had a complexity of $O(L^2)$ where L is the input time series length (Wen et al, 2022) which is considered as a bottleneck. In the following table

we demonstrate

Methods	Training	
	Time	Memory
Transformer [Vaswani 2017]	$\mathcal{O}(L^2)$	$\mathcal{O}(L^2)$
LogTrans [Li, 2019]	$\mathcal{O}(L \log L)$	$\mathcal{O}(L^2)$
Informer [Zhou 2021]	$\mathcal{O}(L \log L)$	$\mathcal{O}(L \log L)$
Pyraformer [Liu 2022]	$\mathcal{O}(L)$	$\mathcal{O}(L)$
FEDformer [Zhou 2022]	$\mathcal{O}(L)$	$\mathcal{O}(L)$
Performer [Chou 2020]	$\mathcal{O}(L \log L)$	$\mathcal{O}(L \log L)$

2.5. Brief analysis of theoretical complexities for our models

2.5.1. REGULAR ATTENTION MECHANISM:

Below are some theoretical approaches that various attention models take based on our literature review.

Let L be the size of an input sequence of tokens. Then regular dot-product attention (Vaswani et al., 2017) is a mapping which accepts matrices $\mathbf{Q}, \mathbf{K}, \mathbf{V} \in \mathbb{R}^{L \times d}$ as input where d is the hidden dimension (dimension of the latent representation). Bidirectional dot-product attention has the following form, where $\mathbf{A} \in \mathbb{R}^{L \times L}$ is the so-called attention matrix:

$$\text{Att}_{\leftrightarrow}(\mathbf{Q}, \mathbf{K}, \mathbf{V}) = \mathbf{D}^{-1} \mathbf{A} \mathbf{V}, \quad \mathbf{A} = \exp\left(\frac{\mathbf{Q} \mathbf{K} \mathbf{K}^{\top}}{\sqrt{d}}\right),$$

$$\mathbf{D} = \text{diag}(\mathbf{A} \mathbf{1}_L).$$

Here $\exp(\cdot)$ is applied elementwise, $\mathbf{1}_L$ is the all-ones vector of length L , and $\text{diag}(\cdot)$ is a diagonal matrix with the input vector as the diagonal. Time and space complexity of computing the above expressions are $O(L^2 d)$ and $O(L^2 + Ld)$ respectively, because \mathbf{A} has to be stored explicitly. Hence, in principle, dot-product attention of this type is incompatible with end-to-end processing of long sequences. Bidirectional attention is applied in encoder self-attention and encoder-decoder attention in Seq2Seq architectures. Another important type of attention is unidirectional dot-product attention which has the form:

$$\text{Att}_{\rightarrow}(\mathbf{Q}, \mathbf{K}, \mathbf{V}) = \tilde{\mathbf{D}}^{-1} \tilde{\mathbf{A}} \mathbf{V}, \quad \tilde{\mathbf{A}} = \text{tril}(\mathbf{A}),$$

$$\tilde{\mathbf{D}} = \text{diag}(\tilde{\mathbf{A}} \mathbf{1}_L),$$

This unidirectional attention is used for autoregressive generative modelling, e.g. as self-attention in generative Transformers as well as the decoder part of Seq2Seq Transformers.

2.5.2. PERFORMER KERNELIZABLE ATTENTION:

The Performer innovative mechanism introduces FAVOR+ that works for attention blocks using matrices $\mathbf{A} \in \mathbb{R}^{L \times L}$ of the form $\mathbf{A}(i, j) = \mathbf{K}(\mathbf{q}_i^{\top}, \mathbf{k}_j^{\top})$, with $\mathbf{q}_i/\mathbf{k}_j$ standing

Figure 1. Approximation of the regular attention mechanism AV (before D-1-renormalization) via (random)feature maps. Dashed-blocks indicate order of computation with corresponding time complexities attached

for the i^{th}/j^{th} query/key row-vector in \mathbf{Q}/\mathbf{K} and kernel $\mathbf{K} : \mathbb{R}^d \times \mathbb{R}^d \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_+$ defined for the (usually randomized) mapping: $\phi : \mathbb{R}^d \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_+^r$ (for some $r > 0$) as:

$$K(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) = \mathbb{E} [\phi(\mathbf{x})^\top \phi(\mathbf{y})].$$

We call $\phi(\mathbf{u})$ a random feature map for $\mathbf{u} \in \mathbb{R}^d$. For $\mathbf{Q}', \mathbf{K}' \in \mathbb{R}^{L \times r}$ with rows given as $\phi(\mathbf{q}_i^\top)^\top$ and $\phi(\mathbf{k}_i^\top)^\top$ respectively, Above equations lead directly to the efficient attention mechanism of the form:

$$\widehat{\text{Att}}_{\leftrightarrow}(\mathbf{Q}, \mathbf{K}, \mathbf{V}) = \widehat{\mathbf{D}}^{-1} \left(\mathbf{Q}' \left((\mathbf{K}')^\top \mathbf{V} \right) \right),$$

$$\widehat{\mathbf{D}} = \text{diag} \left(\mathbf{Q}' \left((\mathbf{K}')^\top \mathbf{1}_L \right) \right).$$

Here $\widehat{\text{Att}}_{\leftrightarrow}$ stands for the approximate attention and brackets indicate the order of computations. It is easy to see that such a mechanism is characterized by space complexity $O(Lr + Ld + rd)$ and time complexity $O(Lrd)$

2.5.3. PROBSPARSE SELF-ATTENTION IN INFORMER:

ProbSparse self-attention by allowing each key to only attend to the u dominant queries:

$$\mathcal{A}(\mathbf{Q}, \mathbf{K}, \mathbf{V}) = \text{Softmax} \left(\frac{\overline{\mathbf{Q}}\mathbf{K}^\top}{\sqrt{d}} \right) \mathbf{V},$$

$$\mathbf{Q} \in \mathbb{R}^{L_Q \times d}, \mathbf{K} \in \mathbb{R}^{L_K \times d}, \mathbf{V} \in \mathbb{R}^{L_V \times d}$$

Where $\overline{\mathbf{Q}}$ is a sparse matrix of the same size of \mathbf{q} and it only contains the Top- u queries under the sparsity measurement $M(\mathbf{q}, \mathbf{K})$. Controlled by a constant sampling factor c , They then set $u = c \cdot \ln L_Q$, which makes the ProbSparse self-attention only need to calculate $O(\ln L_Q)$ dot-product for each query-key lookup and the layer memory usage maintains $O(L_K \ln L_Q)$. Under the multi-head perspective, this attention generates different sparse query-key pairs for each head, which avoids severe information loss in return.

However, the traversing of all the queries for the measurement $M(\mathbf{q}_i, \mathbf{K})$ requires calculating each dot-product pairs,

i.e., quadratically $O(L_Q L_K)$, besides the LSE operation has the potential numerical stability issue. Motivated by this, we propose an empirical approximation for the efficient acquisition of the query sparsity measurement.

2.5.4. PYRAMIDAL ATTENTION MODULE IN PYRAFORMER:

The Pyraformer uses a pyramidal graph to describe the dependencies in a time series data in a multiresolution fashion. The pyramidal graph is made up of two parts: inter-scale connections, which form a C -ary tree with parent nodes having C children, and intra-scale connections, which connect neighboring nodes. This allows for a multi-resolution representation of the original time series, making it easier to capture long-range dependencies at coarser scales.

Original Transformer (Vaswani et al., 2017), using not only dense, but full graph. In contrast, as illustrated below, the pyramidal graph in the proposed Pyraformer reduces the computational cost to $O(L)$ without increasing the order of the maximum length of the signal traversing path.

Figure 2. Pyraformer connections graph, red dotted line stands for maximum signal travelling path.

Original attention output formula could be simplified to:

$$\mathbf{y}_i = \sum_{\ell \in \mathbb{N}_\ell^{(s)}} \frac{\exp(\mathbf{q}_i \mathbf{k}_\ell^\top / \sqrt{d_K}) \mathbf{v}_\ell}{\sum_{\ell \in \mathbb{N}_\ell^{(s)}} \exp(\mathbf{q}_i \mathbf{k}_\ell^\top / \sqrt{d_K})}$$

Where \mathbf{y}_i computed for nodes $n_l^{(s)}$ with corresponding neighbourhood $\mathbb{N}_\ell^{(s)} : \mathbb{N}_\ell^{(s)} = \mathbb{A}_\ell^{(s)} \cup \mathbb{C}_\ell^{(s)} \cup \mathbb{P}_\ell^{(s)}$, comprising adjacent nodes l on same tree depth s , including self-loop $\mathbb{A}_\ell^{(s)}$, children nodes $\mathbb{C}_\ell^{(s)}$ and parenting node $\mathbb{P}_\ell^{(s)}$.

3. Experiments Description

We introduce the range of experiments to be performed and the ideas behind our methodology.

3.1. Preprocessing

We first aim to clean the data in aspects of normalization, timestamp pre-processing and preparation and checks for seasonal trends plus decomposition.

3.2. Creating Embeddings

After initial cleaning of data our next steps would include trying to create embedding for our data and performing experiments with local/global timestamp, fixed position, channel projection.

3.3. Encoding

We want to try multiple encoding architectures with our created embeddings including the previously described Informer and Performer approaches with some other approaches as well to compare our results, these include: Log-Trans, Pyraformer.

3.4. Decoding and Metrics for Evaluation

Lastly our experiments will include trying the decoding architectures for respective encoders listed above and comparing results with initial baselines. We also will try different metrics like RMSE, MSE, MAE, training time and inference time to find the most suitable for comparison in a meaningful way. Moreover, we will provide quantitative comparison of above mentioned models, including estimation of inference speed and memory footprint plus asymptotic analysis.

4. Data

We use high frequency cryptocurrency data that for our experiments. The choice of data was more or less arbitrary but with a primary focus to be simple as we do not want to have data specific issues for such kind of experiments. Therefore, we selected a simple dataset of current market prices sampled at each second from a cryptocurrency exchange. To be specific, it a dataset of sampled best bid and ask prices. We define current market price as a middle price (which is the average of best bid and ask prices). For simplicity, we try predicting the next second price based on the previous one. We consider such simple autoregressive set-up since our primary goal is not to obtain good or best predictions but to analyze the memory and time footprint of different architectures. The dataset contains slightly more than 86000 rows of data.

5. Results

In the following section we discuss empirical results obtained after training 2 transformer models. First, we report the inference speed. It is an average over 1000 runs. We measure current time before the inference and measure current time after the inference. The difference obtained is the elapsed time which we consider as inference speed (**in ms**) and report in Table 1. We do measurements on a local machine due to some issues with Google Colab. The GPU used is Nvidia GTX 1650 Ti. Secondly, we report how much

GPU memory is used during the inference. Since after the inference, GPU does not empty the cache, we can measure the memory footprint by considering the difference of free GPU memory before and after the inference. The result (**in MiB, mebibyte**) is shown in Table 2.

As we can see, the informer shows improvement over the vanilla transformer architecture.

6. Tables & Figures

Error type enc_{seq} length	MAE_{train}	MSE_{train}	$RMSE_{train}$	MAE_{val}	MSE_{val}	$RMSE_{val}$
15	0.344	0.119	0.345	1.032	1.501	1.039
30	0.432	0.191	0.437	1.032	1.501	1.039
60	0.188	0.036	0.189	1.033	1.503	1.040
120	0.180	0.033	0.181	1.034	1.505	1.042
240	0.481	0.233	0.483	1.033	1.497	1.038

Table 1: Baseline TS Transformer metrics table. enc_{seq} stands for length of the contexts that encoder uses to train K, V attention matrices.

Error type enc_{seq} length	MAE_{train}	MSE_{train}	$RMSE_{train}$	MAE_{val}	MSE_{val}	$RMSE_{val}$
15	0.0455	0.0032	0.0568	0.1977	0.1224	0.3498
30	0.0332	0.0017	0.0418	0.1574	0.0864	0.2939
60	0.0284	0.0015	0.0388	0.2286	0.1783	0.4222
120	0.0359	0.0023	0.0485	0.2315	0.1865	0.4319
240	0.0385	0.0027	0.0515	0.2854	0.2459	0.4959

Table 2: Informer metrics report

encoder seq length	15	30	60	120	240
Model					
Baseline	433.82	495.79	825.66	1413.42	2444.71
Informer	83.96	167.93	419.83	839.66	2088.85

Table 3: GPU memory used during inference on one batch of size 256. Measurements are in mebibytes **MiB**

encoder seq length	15	30	60	120	240
Model					
Baseline	139.81	179.52	365.62	645.19	1309.92
Informer	90.65	152.932	294.59	542.22	915.15

Table 4: Inference time measured on Nvidia GTX 1650 Ti. Measurements are in milliseconds **ms**

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Figure 3. memory usage informer vs vanilla transformer

Figure 4. Inference time informer vs vanilla transformer

Figure 5. inference speed informer vs vanilla transformer

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